

ULTRAVIOLET ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF SULPHONES. PART III. EFFECT OF STERIC CONFORMATION

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The ultraviolet absorption spectra of several *o*:*o*'- and *p*:*p*'-disubstituted diphenylsulphones, and *o*:*o*'-disubstituted di-(4-aminophenyl)-sulphones have been determined and analysed. The data suggest that while a slight inhibition of conjugation of the sulphonyl group with the benzene ring is caused by *ortho* substituents in diphenylsulphone, no such inhibition is observed in the case of *o*:*o*'-disubstituted di-(4-aminophenyl)-sulphone. An explanation is offered to account for this difference in their spectral behaviour. It takes into account the geometry of the molecules and the overlapping potentialities of the *zp*-orbital of carbon with the *3d*'-orbital of sulphur when a *2p*-*3d* π -bond is formed between carbon and sulphur in the excited state.

The ultraviolet absorption spectra of arylsulphones indicate strong conjugative interaction of the sulphonyl group with benzene nucleus (Fehnel and Carmack, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 231; Koch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 408; Leandri *et al.*, *Gazzetta*, 1954, 84, 73). Fehnel and Carmack (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1292) reported that this conjugation was not susceptible to steric inhibition.

FIG. 1

Wave-length ($m\mu$).

They considered it probable that utilisation of the $3d$ -orbitals of sulphur permitted the formation of a double bond between sulphur and one or more of the mutually non-planar atoms attached to it. In the present investigation the ultraviolet absorption spectra of several $o:o'$ -disubstituted diarylsulphones have been recorded (Table I) to further examine the steric effects of *ortho* substituents on the conjugation of the sulphonyl group with aromatic nuclei.

Diphenylsulphone exhibits a weak B-band with vibrational structure and a strong K-band with absorption maximum at $235\text{ m}\mu$ (Fig. 1). While studying the effects of substituents on conjugation, it is the K-band that has to be considered. The polar and steric effects reflect on λ_{max} and ϵ_{max} . Instead of analysing the spectral data with reference to both the above quantities, it is preferable to consider oscillator strengths on theoretical grounds. Hence, reference is made to oscillator strengths also in the present discussion. When CH_3 -, Cl -, or CH_3O - group is present in the $p:p'$ -positions of diphenylsulphone (Nos. 5-7 in Table I), there is a red shift of the maximum of the $235\text{ m}\mu$ band and the intensity of the band is also increased. In a more quantitative way this effect may be seen in the oscillator strengths. The *para* substituents are thus seen to promote conjugation. This indeed is to be expected, taking into consideration the electronic nature of the substituents.

TABLE I

Sulphones.	λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .	f .
1. Diphenyl-	274 $\text{m}\mu$	1,300	
	267	2,000	
	261	1,700	
	235	15,800	0.298
2. Di- <i>o</i> -tolyl-	280	2,500	
	273	2,700	
	233	14,500	0.250
3. Di-(2-chlorophenyl)-	285	2,800	
	277	2,900	
	235	13,700	0.192
4. Di-(2-methoxyphenyl)-	289	7,600	
	233*	10,200	0.074
5. Di- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	245	20,100	0.395
	223	10,100	
6. Di-(4-chlorophenyl)-	249	24,300	0.416
	227	13,200	
7. Di-(4-methoxyphenyl)-	260	22,600	0.430
	237	14,600	
8. Di-(4-aminophenyl)-	295	27,800	0.521
	261	17,800	0.274
9. Di-(4-amino-2-methylphenyl)-	291	30,200	0.567
	262	19,100	0.256
10. Di-(4-amino-2-chlorophenyl)-	298	33,100	0.578
	265	18,900	0.235

*Inflection.

FIG. 2

Wave-length (m μ).

FIG. 3

Wave-length, m μ

In the case of *o*:*o'*-disubstituted diphenylsulphones (Nos. 2-4), the same substituents cause a diminution in oscillator strength, *i.e.*, they cause a weakening of conjugation of the benzene nuclei with the sulphonyl group. This is clearly a case of steric inhibition of resonance by *ortho* substituents.

Di-(4-aminophenyl)-sulphone exhibits a strong band (Fig. 3) with absorption maximum at 295 $m\mu$. There is also a weaker band at 261 $m\mu$. The same band structure is observed in the spectra of di-(4-amino-2-methylphenyl)- and di-(4-amino-2-chlorophenyl)-sulphones also. The stronger absorption band in di-(4-aminophenyl)-sulphone seems to originate from electronic excitation involving both the benzene nuclei (I) while the weaker band appears to be due to electronic excitation involving only one benzene ring (II and III).

This view gains support from the fact that *p*-aminophenylmethylsulphone has only one absorption band with maximum at 268 $m\mu$ (λ_{max} 19,300). The λ_{max} and ϵ_{max} of this band correspond to the weaker band of di-(4-aminophenyl)-sulphone (λ_{max} 261 $m\mu$, ϵ_{max} 17,800). Similarly *p*-methoxyphenylmethylsulphone exhibits only one band with maximum at 240 $m\mu$, (λ_{max} 16,500) which corresponds to the weaker band of di-(4-methoxyphenyl)-sulphone (λ_{max} 237 $m\mu$, ϵ_{max} 14,600). We may therefore expect substituents in the *o*:*o'*-positions of di-(4-aminophenyl)-sulphone to exert their influence on both the bands. A comparison of the spectra of di-(4-aminophenyl)-sulphone and its *o*:*o'*-disubstituted derivatives shows that the *ortho* substituents have promoted conjugation of the sulphonyl group with the aryl nuclei. We thus find that in the diphenylsulphone molecule, electron-releasing groups do not increase the oscillator strength when present in *o*:*o'*-positions, while the same groups, when present in *o*:*o'*-positions in di-(4-aminophenyl)-sulphone, cause a significant increase in oscillator strength. This spectral effect can be explained on the basis of the geometric change the molecules undergo by the introduction of substituents.

The planes of the benzene rings were found by X-ray analysis (Toussaint, *Bull. soc. roy. sci. Liege*, 1944, 13, 163; *Chem. Abst.*, 1948, 42, 7128) to be inclined at right angles to the C-S-C plane in di-(4-bromophenyl)-sulphone. Diphenylsulphone also may be expected to have almost the same conformation. When *ortho* substituents are introduced, the benzene rings may no longer be perpendicular to the C-S-C plane, but may be twisted due to repulsion arising

between the *ortho* substituents. The extent to which the rings are twisted depends upon the size of the groups. The conjugation of the sulphonyl group with the benzene ring thus seems to be intimately connected with the angle between the C-S-C plane and the plane of the benzene ring. The presence of *ortho* substituents by itself does not seem to inhibit conjugation provided that the geometry of the molecule favours conjugation. This view gains support from the fact that *ortho* substituents in di-(4-aminophenyl)-sulphone do not inhibit conjugation; they actually enhance conjugation. All these facts may be understood by considering the overlapping potentialities of the *d*-orbital of sulphur atom with the *p*-orbital of the adjacent carbon atom when a double bond is formed. When the plane of the benzene ring is perpendicular to the C-S-C plane, the axis of maximum density of the *p*-orbital of the π -electron (C atom) will be perpendicular to the benzene plane. This will favour maximum overlapping with the *3d*-orbital of sulphur.

When the plane of the benzene ring is tilted by a small angle, the overlapping of the *p*- and *d*-orbitals becomes less. The inhibition of conjugation, caused by

FIG. 4

Overlapping of the *2p*-orbital of carbon with the *3d*-orbital of sulphur.

the introduction of electron-releasing substituents in *o*:*o'*-positions in diphenylsulphone, must be attributed to the tilt the benzene rings undergo from their original positions due to repulsion between the *ortho* groups. In the case of *o*:*o'*-disubstituted di-(4-aminophenyl)-sulphones, the *para*-amino groups exercise an influence to overcome the steric repulsion. This view can be substantiated by considering the spectral characteristics of *ortho*-substituted nitrobenzenes and 3-substituted 4-nitroanilines (Table II). The presence of CH_3 - and Cl - in the *ortho*-positions results in a decrease of oscillator strength of nitrobenzene by 31% and 60% respectively. The same groups, when present *ortho* to the nitro group in 4-nitroaniline, decrease the oscillator strength to the extent of 8% and 19% only. Thus, it is evident that the *para*-amino group, by promoting conjugation and thus increasing resonance energy, has annulled the *ortho*-steric effect partially. In the case of diphenylsulphone, the steric effect exerted by *ortho* substituents is evidently of a small magnitude, and hence, the *para*-amino groups are able to suppress it completely.

TABLE II

		λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .	<i>f</i> .
Nitrobenzene	...	261 $\text{m}\mu$	8,300	0.249
2-Methylnitrobenzene	...	259	5,250	0.171
2-Chloronitrobenzene	...	253	3,500	0.100
4-Nitroaniline	...	380	15,500	0.376*
3-Methyl-4-nitroaniline	...	372	11,100	0.345
		257	5,000	
		236	5,700	
3-Chloro-4-nitroaniline	...	374	13,400	0.303
		233	6,100	

* Webster, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1957, 76, 367.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Diphenyl- and di-*p*-tolyl-sulphones were prepared by the methods of Hinsberg (*Ber.*, 1910, 43, 289) and Beckurts and Otto (*ibid.*, 1878, 11, 2068), respectively. Di-*o*-tolyl-, di-(4-chloro-2-methylphenyl)- and di-(4-amino-2-methylphenyl)-sulphones were prepared as described by Balasubramanian and Baliah (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 1253). Di-(4-chlorophenyl)-sulphone, m. p. 146-47°, was prepared from *p*-chlorobenzenesulphonyl chloride and chlorobenzene by the Friedel-Crafts reaction (Beckurts and Otto, *loc. cit.*). Di-(4-methoxyphenyl)-sulphone, m. p. 123-29°, was prepared similarly from *p*-methoxybenzenesulphonyl chloride and anisole.² Di-(2-methoxyphenyl)-sulphone, m. p. 196-97°, was prepared according to Mauthner (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 1350). Di-(2-chlorophenyl)-sulphone, m. p. 185-86°, and di-(4-amino-2-chlorophenyl)-sulphone, m. p. 262-63°, were prepared in our laboratories by Mr. A. Ekambaram (unpublished work). Di-(4-aminophenyl)-sulphone was prepared by the method of Sugawara and Sakurai (*J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1940, 60, 22).

Ultraviolet Absorption Measurements.—The ultraviolet absorption spectra were determined with a Beckman quartz spectrophotometer, model DU. The solvent used was 96% ethanol.

The oscillator strengths, *f*, were computed from the integrated areas under the curves by use of the equation

$$f = 4.32 \times 10^{-9} \int \epsilon d\nu$$

where ϵ is the molar extinction coefficient and ν is the wave-number in cm^{-1} . For a given band, the area was measured under the two minima on each side of the band.

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